

uMed: Your Choice

Developed by: Institute for Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine,

UZH Digital Society Initiative Zürich,

Koboldgames GmbH

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Keywords

Cognitive Bias, Empathy, End-of-life Decisions, Ethical Decision-making, Health, Medical Ethics

Figure 1. Screenshot from *uMed: Your Choice* (Koboldgames GmbH and UZH Digital Society Initiative Zürich). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

uMed: Your Choice (see Figure 1) is a serious moral game developed in cooperation with the Institute for Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine and the UZH Digital Society Initiative Zürich (Christen et al., 2021).

Players follow the story as young medical assistants and make decisions about patients' well-being and their interactions with patients, staff, and relatives.

The primary focus is to improve moral sensitivity, integrity, and professional decision-making. It was developed for medical students in clinical ethics courses and serves as a complementary

educational tool. Its dialog-based gameplay allows participants to make decisions and explore different outcomes (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). uMed emphasizes self-study combined with reflective group discussions, aligning with the ethos of serious games to foster engagement and applied learning (Christen et al., 2021). Therefore, it combines content on medical ethics with game features like rules/goals, fantasy, challenge, sensory stimuli, and player autonomy. With feedback and reflection, the game fosters sustained motivation and ethical reasoning (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022; Caserman et al., 2020).

Facts

Release date:	2019
Developer:	Institute for Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine, UZH Digital Society Initiative Zürich, Koboldgames GmbH
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	can be played alone as well as in small groups of 8–9 players
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	The estimated playtime for one person is about 90 minutes; if played in small-groups, discussion sessions usually take longer.
Languages:	German
Environment:	Any device with a pointing device; works on Windows and macOS.
Material:	The game itself is explained in the introduction; only a device such as a computer, tablet, or phone is required. The player needs to be able to click on action and dialogue options. There is a handbook for teachers.
Price:	The game is not publicly available for playing, but can be played as part of a course at universities

Resonance & Criticism

The University of Zürich's medical students' ethics curriculum now includes uMed, which is increasingly recognized as a tool for medical ethics teaching (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). As it incorporates interactivity and reflection, which previous approaches do not, it is seen as an innovative approach to teaching ethics (Katsarov et al., 2020).

Overall user numbers are not given, but 270 students used it during their studies in 2021 (Christen et al., 2021). According to feedback, the game is enjoyable and beneficial for both teachers and students (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022).

However, the scoring system has been criticized for potentially oversimplifying complex moral decisions, leading to debates about its effectiveness in assessing morality (Katsarov et al., 2020).

Game Principle & Process

The game's visual landscape is a static 2D space with limited interaction options. To progress, players must choose between laudable and problematic dialogue and action options and investigate still scenes. In-game responses vary depending on the user's choices. A scoring system provides immediate feedback after each scene. It consists of lightning bolts, which indicate effectiveness regarding objectives; laurels, which represent integrity and accountability; and hearts, which measure empathy and interpersonal happiness. They further show how different values and expectations can collide and conflict in practice (Christen et al., 2021).

Players receive a debriefing session following each scenario, during which their results are reviewed and explained verbally to facilitate reflection (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022).

uMed introduces characters, including other medical personnel, patients, and their relatives. Players experiment with their behavior in a safe yet realistic environment, simulating the pressures and ethical challenges of medical practice (Katsarov et al., 2020). The game's design does not require advanced medical knowledge, making it accessible to a broader audience while still being relevant to medical professionals (Christen et al., 2021).

Dynamic thought experiments that encourage thinking about appropriate medical treatment are part of the game elements. Players usually follow what they believe to be socially acceptable or ethically ideal behaviors during their first sessions, underscoring the need for personal moral reflection. The instructional design incorporates action-based learning to foster ethical awareness and decision-making skills, drawing heavily on ideas from moral psychology, such as "moral intelligence". As players debate their choices and results in groups under teacher supervision, social interaction is a crucial aspect (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022; Katsarov et al., 2020).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Overall, the game aims to sensitize participants to the value conflicts inherent in medical practice and to complement existing medical training by addressing five goals that are difficult to achieve within the current curriculum (Christen et al., 2021). These goals are empathic concern, awareness of cognitive biases, development of moral schemas, sensitivity to moral disengagement, and moral courage. They align with the concept of "moral intelligence," which synthesizes research in moral psychology into a coherent educational framework (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022).

It is done through action-based learning where players decide, imagine outcomes, and consider the repercussions. The game also uses mechanisms such as placing players in a realistic environment as newly-graduated doctors beginning their residency, thereby enhancing the transfer of knowledge and skills into practice. Players can personalize their character by selecting a name and gender or adopt a different identity, encouraging

engagement and self-reflection. This immersive role-playing fosters empathy and moral development, enabling players to explore diverse perspectives and ethical challenges (Christen et al., 2021).

Teachers are essential in helping students reflect and connect ethical theory to gaming. Students play scenarios either alone or in small groups and then use guided questions and conversations to reflect on their experiences (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022).

Effectiveness

The game has been successful in fostering moral sensitivity and attentiveness to ethical dilemmas (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). Research indicates that after playing the game, players demonstrated increased respect for patient autonomy and the capacity to identify ethical dilemmas in clinical practice (Christen et al., 2021). These results were observed after just two hours of play, demonstrating the game's effectiveness in teaching ethics (Eichinger et al., 2022).

A study conducted in labs and classrooms has demonstrated that "uMed" is more effective than other digital training resources at promoting ethical awareness and reasoning. According to students' qualitative responses, the game increased their awareness of ethical dilemmas in work environments and was seen as a crucial educational resource (Christen et al., 2021). The game's immersive design induces a state of flow, engaging players through well-balanced obstacles that prompt the recall of ethical principles (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). Players continue to exhibit heightened ethical awareness weeks after playing, according to follow-up research (Christen et al., 2021).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game's scoring system serves as feedback on the character's actions, but this could lead players to mistakenly believe it offers absolute moral judgments (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). To avoid bias during games, sensitive subjects such as discrimination and resource allocation must be carefully handled. Since the game is not currently accessible in various languages, accessibility may be limited by language barriers (Christen et al., 2021). Furthermore, without appropriate instruction, audiences outside healthcare training may find it challenging to understand ethical issues (Eichinger & Katsarov, 2022). Before-and-after discussions are also essential, as otherwise users may assume that completing the game equates to having mastered the relevant moral skills (Christen et al., 2021).

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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